

Research on zero power reactor neutron noise based on reactor Monte Carlo Code RMC

Yuanhao Gou¹, Ganglin Yu ^{1*}, Conglong Jia², Zhe Chuan Tan¹, Dacai Zhang¹, Junxiao Zhang¹, Kan Wang¹

¹Department of Engineering Physics, Tsinghua University Beijing, 100084, China; ²School of Nuclear Science and Engineering, North China Electric Power University Beijing, 102206, China

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803275

ABSTRACT

The prompt neutron decay constant α , a key reactor dynamic parameter, is of great importance for reactor safety analysis and the evaluation of dynamical behavior. Its accurate determination is therefore an essential component of reactor physics experiments. Zero power reactor neutron noise analysis methods constitute an effective class of techniques for measuring the α value. These methods are based on the statistical fluctuations induced by individual neutron chains. By measuring and analyzing the characteristics of these fluctuations, reactor dynamic parameters can be inferred. To ensure that individual fission chains do not overlap excessively and remain observable, zero power reactor neutron noise analysis techniques require the reactor power to be sufficiently low. Commonly used methods of this type include the Rossi- α and Feynman- α approaches. In this study, a capture-time output module was newly implemented in RMC, the Monte Carlo code independently developed by Tsinghua University, together with functionalities to calculate the prompt neutron decay constant using the Rossi- α and Feynman- α methods. Based on these newly developed features, validation studies were conducted using measurement data from Tsinghua University's subcritical experimental assembly, and simulations were performed for systems with different fuel-rod configurations. The simulated prompt neutron decay constants exhibit good agreement with the experimental results, thereby demonstrating the reliability and accuracy of RMC in calculating the α parameter. Then, the results of calculating the subcriticality using the Rossi- α and Feynman- α methods were analyzed.

Keywords: RMC, reactor noise, rossi- α , feynman- α

NOMENCLATURE

α	The prompt neutron decay time constant	τ	The time interval using in Feynman- α method
β_{eff}	The effective fraction of delayed neutrons	\bar{c}	The average countings in time interval
Δ	The time interval	c	The measured neutron count
ϵ	The detection efficiency	c_i	The countings at the i-th time interval
Λ	The neutron generation time	D_v	The Diven's parameter
ν	The neutrons per fission	F	The average fission rate
p_c	The probability of detected correlated neutron pairs	p_r	The probability of detected uncorrelated neutron pairs
p	The total detection probability of neutron pairs	ρ	The reactivity
k_p	The prompt neutron multiplication factor	Σ_f	The macroscopic fission cross section
l	The prompt neutron lifetime	N	The number of samples
Y	The additional correlation term in Feynman- α method	V	The neutron flight velocity

*yuganglin@tsinghua.edu.cn

1. INTRODUCTION

The task of reactor physics experiments is to study the neutron multiplication caused by the interaction of large numbers of neutrons with the nuclei of the medium, as well as the laws of neutron motion within the medium. Based on these laws, the physical parameters of the reactor and related nuclear properties are determined. Therefore, reactor physics experiments are often integral in nature. With the development of nuclear technology, the application of stochastic techniques in reactor science and technology has become an important branch of reactor physics experiments, known as reactor noise analysis. Zero power reactor neutron noise is primarily caused by the random nature of nuclear reactions, such as the statistical fluctuations in the number of neutrons released during each fission reaction. From the perspective of reactor dynamics, this is equivalent to a fluctuating equivalent neutron source. When neutrons are detected by the detector, the detector's output signal fluctuates. Zero power reactor neutron noise analysis techniques investigate the variations in counts caused by individual chain neutrons. Based on these patterns, reactor dynamic parameters can be determined, which are used to measure prompt neutron decay time constants, reactivity, and the effective fraction of delayed neutrons.

Based on Tsinghua University's independently developed Monte Carlo code RMC, a capture time output function was implemented, along with Rossi-alpha and Feynman-alpha calculation capabilities for determining the prompt neutron decay constant[1, 2, 3]. Using the developed prompt neutron decay constant calculation module, the results were validated against experimental data from Tsinghua University's subcritical assembly, showing good agreement between simulation and experiment. Then, the results of calculating the subcriticality using the Rossi- α and Feynman- α methods were analyzed.

2. METHOD

Next, the capture event output, and the Rossi- α and Feynman- α methods are introduced.

2.1. Capture Event Output

In reactor physics experiments, thermal neutrons are primarily detected using ^3He detectors, primarily through the (n,p) reaction between thermal neutrons and ^3He . Zero power reactor neutron noise analysis requires analyzing the time series of the ^3He reaction. Therefore, the time of captured neutrons within this neutron history needs to be developed in RMC. Table I shows the output results of the capture event output function of RMC. The output in Table I shows the cell number, capture time, and capture coordinates of the captured neutron in each neutron history. If the neutron is captured by the specified nuclide in the specified cell, the cell number is non-zero; otherwise, if the neutron is not captured or is captured by an unspecified nuclide outside the specified cell, the cell number is set to zero[1].

By utilizing the detection times of emitted neutrons captured by the detector, in conjunction with the Poissonian temporal characteristics of source events, a complete sequence of neutron detection pulses can be generated.

2.2. Rossi-alpha Method

The Rossi-alpha method is non-destructive and can monitor the prompt neutron decay constant without disturbing the reactor, thereby achieving reactor control and protection. Furthermore, the method has a wide range of applicability, demonstrating excellent versatility and flexibility in applications such as thermal and fast neutron reactors[4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

The prompt neutron decay time constant can be expressed by α , and the expression of prompt neutron decay time α can be expressed by the Eq. 1. It can be seen from the Eq. 1 that the prompt neutron decay constant of a subcritical reactor is positive.

Table I. RMC Capture Event Results

History Number	Cell Number	Times (Shakes/ 10^{-8} s)	Capture Position(x, y, z)(cm)
1	24	179.71	(1.42,-10.93,-3.98)
1	21	1247.25	(-8.79,-6.78,-15.61)
1	0	0	(8.53,-18.09,0.15)
1	0	0	(-17.74,-9.23,-9.72)
2	0	0	(-11.13,-16.62,14.55)
2	0	0	(-0.19,19.99,0.22)
3	0	0	(13.53,-14.73,-7.44)
3	0	0	(11.95,-16.04,10.55)
3	0	0	(3.71,5.07,-30.00)
4	0	0	(-17.72,-9.27,-18.19)
4	0	0	(-17.72,-9.27,-18.19)
4	0	0	(-17.72,-9.27,-18.19)
4	0	0	(-17.72,-9.27,-18.19)
5	0	0	(6.93,18.76,0.31)
5	0	0	(13.66,14.61,3.31)
5	18	5732.63	(-12.09,5.14,8.31)
5	14	6041.94	(3.13,11.27,4.02)
5	0	0	(5.70,19.17,11.21)

$$\alpha = (-\rho + \beta_{eff}) / \Lambda \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Correlated and uncorrelated neutron

As shown in the Figure 1, if fission occurs at time t_0 , then the number of correlated neutron pairs (A, B) detected by detectors 1 and 2 respectively during the time interval Δ between t_1 and t_2 can be expressed by the Eq. 2[6].

$$p_c(t_1, t_2) \Delta^2 = F \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 \frac{D_v}{2l} \frac{k_p^2}{1 - k_p} e^{-\alpha t} \quad (2)$$

The uncorrelated neutron pairs (A, C) can be expressed by the Eq. 3. Hence, the total neutron population can be represented as the sum of uncorrelated and correlated neutrons, as shown in the Eq. 4. It can be further simplified into Eq. 5, where $\bar{m} = (F\Delta)^2 \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2$, $A = F \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 \frac{D_v}{2l} \frac{k_p^2}{1 - k_p}$.

$$p_r(t_1, t_2) \Delta^2 = F \epsilon_1 \Delta F \epsilon_2 \Delta = (F\Delta)^2 \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 \quad (3)$$

$$p(t_1, t_2) \Delta^2 = (F\Delta)^2 \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 + F\epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 \frac{D_v}{2l} \frac{k_p^2}{1 - k_p} e^{-\alpha t} \quad (4)$$

$$P(t) = \bar{m} + Ae^{-\alpha t} \quad (5)$$

2.3. Feynman-alpha Method

The neutron source introduced into the subcritical system emits neutrons randomly, and its statistical behavior follows a Poisson distribution [9, 10, 11, 12, 13]. However, the statistical behavior of neutrons inside the reactor deviates from the Poisson distribution due to the presence of correlated neutrons. The degree of neutron correlation is reflected in the ratio between the variance and the mean of neutron counts. Therefore, the variance-to-mean ratio serves as an important physical quantity for evaluating statistical fluctuations. The expressions for the variance and the variance-to-mean ratio are shown in the Eq. 6 and 7.

$$\overline{S^2} = \sum_{i=1}^N [c_i - \bar{c}]^2 / N = \overline{c^2} - \bar{c}^2 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\overline{S^2}}{\bar{c}} = \frac{\overline{c^2} - \bar{c}^2}{\bar{c}} \quad (7)$$

In contrast, for neutrons within the reactor, if the measured neutron count c over a time interval τ deviates from the Poisson distribution, the ratio of variance to mean will no longer be 1; instead, an additional correlation term Y must be added as shown in the Eq. 8 [14].

$$\frac{\overline{S^2}}{\bar{c}} = \frac{\overline{c^2} - \bar{c}^2}{\bar{c}} = 1 + Y \quad (8)$$

By integrating Eq 4, the Eq 9 can be obtained.

$$\frac{\overline{c^2} - \bar{c}^2}{2} = \int_{t_2=0}^{\tau} \int_{t_1=0}^{t_2} p(t_1, t_2) dt_1 dt_2 = \frac{F^2 \epsilon^2 \tau^2}{2} + \frac{F \epsilon^2 D_v k_p^2 \tau}{2(1 - k_p)^2} \left(1 - \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha \tau}}{\alpha \tau}\right) \quad (9)$$

According to the definition, $F\epsilon\tau = \bar{c}$. Substituting $F\epsilon\tau = \bar{c}$ into Eq. 9 and moving the first term on the right-hand side to the left-hand side yields Eq. 10.

$$Y = \frac{\overline{c^2} - \bar{c}^2}{\bar{c}} - 1 = \frac{\epsilon k_p^2 D_v}{(1 - k_p)^2} \left[1 - \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha \tau}}{\alpha \tau}\right] \quad (10)$$

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The subcritical device in the Reactor Physics Laboratory of Tsinghua University were experimentally investigated and compared with theoretical calculations. The core is constructed of plexiglass and uranium rods, measuring 35.6 x 35.6 x 60 cm in length, width, and height respectively. A graphite reflector is placed on the outside of the core. There are 256 (16 x 16) fuel element channels, each 1 cm in diameter. Sixteen holes in the four corners of the core have been filled with plexiglass rods, allowing for a maximum of 240 fuel rods to ensure subcritical operation [15]. The reactor core and detector are shown in

Fig 2. The experiment measured α values for 26 loading conditions with 144 to 240 fuel rods. The experiment used a ^3He detector and an Am-Be neutron source. The experimental setup was modeled using RMC, and the prompt neutron decay time constants for 26 different loading conditions were calculated. The RMC modelled diagram is shown in the Fig 3. The nuclear data library used for this calculation is ENDF/B-VII.1 and the fission multiplicity model used in this simulation is LLNL [16].

Figure 2. RMC modelled diagram

Figure 3. RMC modelled diagram

In the experiments, the prompt neutron decay time constant was calculated using the Rossi- α method for 26 different fuel rods configurations, while the Feynman- α method was used to calculate the prompt neutron decay time constant for only 10 fuel rods configurations. Figure 4 shows the fitting curves of the Rossi-alpha and Feynman-alpha methods for the 168-fuel-rod configuration. The results obtained using the Rossi- α and Feynman- α methods are shown in the Table II and III. It can be seen that the experimental values agree well with the calculated results, demonstrating the correctness of the implemented functionalities.

The prompt neutron decay time constant can be used to determine the reactivity of a subcritical reactor.

 (a) Rossi- α Results

 (b) Feynman- α Results

 Figure 4. Fitting results of the Rossi- α and Feynman- α methods for the 168 fuel rod configuration

 Table II. Comparison of the calculated prompt neutron decay time constant with the experimental value using Rossi- α method

Fuel rods	RMC (s^{-1})	Exp. (s^{-1})	Error	Fuel rods	RMC (s^{-1})	Exp. (s^{-1})	Error
240	141.47 ± 0.69	139.09 ± 0.38	1.71%	216	347.80 ± 1.51	356.82 ± 1.73	-2.53%
239	150.13 ± 0.66	146.27 ± 0.81	2.64%	212	389.10 ± 1.46	393.43 ± 1.72	-1.10%
238	156.76 ± 0.77	159.53 ± 0.72	-1.74%	208	427.83 ± 2.12	429.80 ± 1.91	-0.46%
237	166.53 ± 0.60	164.79 ± 0.79	1.06%	204	467.35 ± 2.70	471.16 ± 2.96	-0.81%
236	176.36 ± 0.71	177.70 ± 0.71	-0.75%	200	506.21 ± 2.67	506.67 ± 3.03	-0.09%
235	182.34 ± 0.99	183.45 ± 0.87	-0.61%	196	543.19 ± 3.78	546.53 ± 3.5	-0.61%
234	191.37 ± 0.79	194.17 ± 0.89	-1.44%	192	586.60 ± 3.71	602.86 ± 4.54	-2.70%
233	200.16 ± 0.98	200.31 ± 0.97	-0.07%	184	651.24 ± 4.89	644.64 ± 4.19	1.02%
232	206.45 ± 1.10	211.48 ± 0.9	-2.38%	176	718.62 ± 8.58	704.08 ± 8.02	2.07%
230	224.53 ± 1.54	229.38 ± 0.8	-2.11%	168	792.33 ± 8.96	798.23 ± 10.34	-0.74%
228	241.42 ± 1.37	244.55 ± 0.96	-1.28%	160	867.89 ± 9.16	821.21 ± 10.26	5.68%
224	277.34 ± 1.96	282.37 ± 1.43	-1.78%	152	949.63 ± 13.04	915.33 ± 13.26	3.75%
220	314.3 ± 1.49	319.84 ± 1.35	-1.73%	144	1032.82 ± 19.12	1035.92 ± 19.34	-0.30%

 Table III. Comparison of the calculated prompt neutron time decay constant with the experimental value using Feynman- α method

Fuel rods	Exp. (s^{-1})	RMC (s^{-1})	Error	Fuel rods	Exp. (s^{-1})	RMC (s^{-1})	Error
240	137.44 ± 8.26	133.18 ± 1.42	-3.10%	220	304.84 ± 6.60	305.69 ± 1.19	0.28%
238	153.37 ± 3.11	151.57 ± 0.99	-1.17%	216	359.17 ± 0.82	341.94 ± 1.34	-4.80%
236	174.73 ± 5.87	167.65 ± 1.04	-4.05%	208	436.44 ± 1.65	416.54 ± 1.64	-4.56%
228	237.98 ± 3.72	233.97 ± 1.31	-1.69%	192	611.69 ± 4.91	572.14 ± 2.28	-6.47%
224	277.52 ± 1.04	267.38 ± 1.43	-3.65%	168	792.18 ± 2.74	776.69 ± 2.84	-1.96%

Therefore, the reactivity inferred using the prompt neutron decay time constant is compared with the true reactivity value obtained from Monte Carlo criticality calculations. The results are shown in the Figure 5. The baseline reactivity is reactivity for the system using the RMC kcode simulations. The Calculated reactivity is the reactivity calculated using α . The β_{eff} and Λ can thus be calculated from the Iterated Fission Probability Method using RMC. From the Figure 5, it can be seen that as the subcriticality deepens, although the baseline reactivity and the calculated reactivity remain linear, the deviation between them becomes significantly larger in deep subcritical conditions than in shallow subcritical conditions. Further research could explore transition from linear to nonlinear, which would be of great help in determining the scope of rossi- α and Feynman- α application.

(a) Rossi- α Results

(b) Feynman- α Results

Figure 5. The relationship between baseline reactivity and calculated Reactivity

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper conducted simulation and experimental studies based on Tsinghua University's independently developed Monte Carlo code, RMC, and the Tsinghua University subcritical facility. First, a capture time output function was developed in RMC. Secondly, a post-processing script for time series processing using the Rossi- α and Feynman- α method was developed. The prompt neutron decay time constant was obtained, which agrees well with the experimental values, demonstrating the correctness of the development. Further work will investigate the applicability of the Rossi- α and Feynman- α methods in subcriticality calculations, as well as improvements to both methods.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Project No. 12405208 and Grant No. 12375169).

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Gou, C. Jia, Z. Liu, and K. Wang. "Simulation of Neutron Multiplicity Counting Based on Monte Carlo Code RMC." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, volume 199(sup1), pp. S485–S499 (2025).
- [2] K. Wang, Z. Liu, N. An, H. Luo, C. Jia, P. Shen, S. Jiang, Y. Hu, Y. Gou, W. Wang, et al. "The Reactor

- Monte Carlo code RMC: The state-of-the-art technologies, advancements, applications, and next." *EPJ Nuclear Sciences & Technologies*, **volume 10**, p. 24 (2024).
- [3] Y. Gou, C. Jia, D. Zhang, Z. Tan, and K. Wang. "Simulation of UNCL experimental device for the reactor fuels based on reactor Monte Carlo code RMC." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 443**, p. 114316 (2025).
- [4] D. Babala. "On the theory of Rossi-alpha experiment in reactor noise studies." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 26**(3), pp. 418–419 (1966).
- [5] D. Babala. "Point-reactor theory of Rossi-alpha experiment." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 28**(2), pp. 237–242 (1967).
- [6] I. McKenzie and G. Espy. "Limits on Subcritical Reactivity Determination using Rossi- α and Related Methods." Technical report, Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), Los Alamos, NM (United States) (2018).
- [7] G. McKenzie. *Modern rossi alpha measurements*. Ph.D. thesis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign (2015).
- [8] V. A. Grabeznoy, V. A. Dulin, V. V. Dulin, and G. M. Mikhailov. "On the determination of neutron multiplication by the Rossi-alpha method." *Nuclear Energy and Technology*, **volume 7**(3), pp. 253–257 (2021).
- [9] T. H. Shin, J. Hutchinson, R. Bahran, and S. A. Pozzi. "A note on the nomenclature in neutron multiplicity mathematics." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 193**(6), pp. 663–679 (2019).
- [10] J. A. Thie. "Random Processes in Nuclear Reactors." (1977).
- [11] C. Dubi and R. Atar. "A stochastic differential equation for neutron count with detector dead time and applications to the Feynman- α formula." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 128**, pp. 380–389 (2019).
- [12] S. Degweker and R. Rudra. "On the relation between Rossi alpha and Feynman alpha methods." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 94**, pp. 433–439 (2016).
- [13] I. Pázsit, Y. Kitamura, J. Wright, and T. Misawa. "Calculation of the pulsed Feynman-alpha formulae and their experimental verification." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 32**(9), pp. 986–1007 (2005).
- [14] Y. Rana and S. Degweker. "Feynman-alpha and Rossi-alpha formulas with delayed neutrons for subcritical reactors driven by pulsed non-Poisson sources." *Nuclear science and engineering*, **volume 162**(2), pp. 117–133 (2009).
- [15] Y. xin, Y. Ganglin, and W. Kan. "Study on Rossi- α measurement method of dynamic parameters of subcritical experimental setup." *Nuclear Power Engineering*, **volume 32**(5), pp. 9–12 (2011).
- [16] J. M. Verbeke, C. Hagmann, and D. Wright. "Simulation of neutron and gamma ray emission from fission and photofission. LLNL Fission Library 2.0. 2." *Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, Tech Rep UCRL-AR-228518-REV-1* (2016).